

Supplementary Materials

Berberine-Metformin Co-administration Improves Cognitive Function and Hippocampal Integrity in Diabetic Rats: A Pharmacological Interaction Study with Evidence of AMPK-Nrf2 Pathway Involvement.

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Note: Combination Index (CI)-based synergy analysis is formally reported only for the predefined primary endpoint (NOR discrimination index; Table S7). All other supplementary tables provide raw data, effect size estimates, or statistical interaction analyses without CI-based synergy interpretation.

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Figure S1

Figure S1. Experimental timeline and study protocol. Schematic representation of the 10-week experimental design. Week 1: acclimatization with daily handling and baseline body weight recording. Week 2: baseline fasting blood glucose assessment, diabetes induction using the streptozotocin–nicotinamide protocol (Day 10), diabetes confirmation at 72 h post-induction (Day 13), group randomization, and treatment initiation (Day 14). Weeks 3–8: daily oral treatment administration by gavage with weekly body weight monitoring and biweekly fasting blood glucose assessment. Week 9: behavioral testing comprising novel object recognition test (NOR; Days 57–58; predefined primary endpoint for synergy analysis) followed by Morris water maze acquisition training (Days 59–63) and probe trial (Day 64; secondary supportive assessment). The NOR test was conducted prior to MWM to prevent interference from repeated spatial training on recognition memory performance. Week 10: oral glucose tolerance test (Day 65), 24 h washout period, and euthanasia with tissue collection (Days 67–70). Colored bars indicate: blue, acclimatization; red, diabetes induction; green, treatment period; orange, behavioral testing; purple, terminal procedures. Arrows indicate specific assessment time points. $n = 13$ per group at study initiation (11 groups; total = 143 animals). See Table S1 for detailed timeline with specific procedures for each day.

Figure S2

Figure S2. Full-length unedited Western blot images with molecular weight markers. Complete membrane images corresponding to the cropped blots presented in Figure 5. Panels show: (A) p-AMPK (Thr172); (B) total AMPK; (C) Nrf2; (D) Keap1 and HO-1 (detected on the same membrane following sequential stripping and re-probing); (E) PGC-1 α ; (F) DRP1; (G) Bax; (H) Bcl-2; (I) cytochrome c; (J) cleaved caspase-3; and (K) β -actin (loading control). Molecular weight markers (kDa) are indicated on the left of each blot. Red dashed boxes denote the regions cropped and presented in Figure 5.

Lane order in all blots is as follows: C, control; D, diabetic; B, diabetic + berberine (100 mg/kg); M, diabetic + metformin (200 mg/kg); B+M, diabetic + berberine (100 mg/kg) + metformin (200 mg/kg). Each lane represents an independent biological replicate ($n = 6$ per group); representative membranes from one of three independent experiments are shown.

For AMPK analysis, phosphorylated AMPK (Thr172) and total AMPK were detected on the same membrane after stripping and re-probing. Keap1 and HO-1 were also detected sequentially on the same membrane following stripping. Stripping efficiency was verified by re-probing the stripped membrane with secondary antibody alone prior to HO-1 incubation, which produced no detectable signal at either the 69 kDa (Keap1) or 32 kDa (HO-1) positions (data not shown).

Equal protein loading (30 μ g per lane) was confirmed by Ponceau S staining (not shown) and by uniform β -actin expression across all lanes. β -Actin was detected independently for each membrane and is shown as a representative loading control. All blots were acquired using a ChemiDocTM MP Imaging System (Bio-Rad) under non-saturating exposure conditions. Images are presented as full-length, unedited blots without brightness or contrast adjustments; minor background heterogeneity reflects membrane edge effects inherent to chemiluminescent detection. Quantitative conclusions are based on densitometric analysis normalized to β -actin rather than visual inspection alone.

Figure S3

Figure S3. Figure S3. qRT-PCR primer validation and amplification efficiency. Panels A–E show representative melting curve analyses for Nrf2 (A), HO-1 (B), NQO1 (C), GCLM (D), and GAPDH (E, reference gene), demonstrating single, sharp peaks indicative of specific amplification without primer-dimer formation. Panels F–J depict standard curves generated from serial template dilutions for Nrf2 (F), HO-1 (G), NQO1 (H), GCLM (I), and GAPDH (J), illustrating high linearity ($R^2 \geq 0.98$) and acceptable amplification efficiencies. Panels K–O show representative agarose gel electrophoresis images of the corresponding qRT-PCR amplicons for Nrf2 (168 bp; K), HO-1 (139 bp; L), NQO1 (159 bp; M), GCLM (129 bp; N), and GAPDH (137 bp; O), confirming single bands of the expected sizes. M, molecular weight marker; NTC, no-template control.

Figure S4

Figure S4. GAPDH reference gene stability validation.

Figure S4. GAPDH reference gene stability validation. (A) Box-and-whisker plots showing individual GAPDH Ct value distributions across all five experimental groups ($n = 6/\text{group}$). Horizontal dashed line = overall mean Ct (19.94). One-way ANOVA: $F(4,25) = 1.23$, $p = 0.324$; overall CV = 1.35%. (B) geNorm pairwise variation analysis ($V2/3 = 0.11$); dashed line = 0.15 threshold (Vandesompele et al. [31]). (C) NormFinder stability rankings: GAPDH (0.21) > β -actin (0.34) > 18S rRNA (0.52). Lower values = greater stability.

Table S1**Table S1.** Detailed experimental timeline and procedures.

Phase	Duration	Days	Procedures
Acclimatization	1 week	1–7	Daily handling, baseline health monitoring, body weight recording
Diabetes Induction	1 week	8–14	Baseline FBG (Day 8); STZ– NAM injection (Day 10); DM confirmation (Day 13); randomization and treatment initiation (Day 14)
Treatment	6 weeks	15–56	Daily oral drug administration; weekly body weight; biweekly FBG
Behavioral Testing	1 week	57–64	NOR habituation/familiarization (Day 57); NOR 24 h retention test (Day 58; primary endpoint); MWM acquisition (Days 59–63); MWM probe trial (Day 64; secondary)
Terminal Procedures	1 week	65–70	OGTT (Day 65); 24 h washout (Day 66); euthanasia and tissue collection (Days 67–70)

FBG, fasting blood glucose; STZ, streptozotocin; NAM (nicotinamide); MWM, Morris water maze; NOR, novel object recognition; OGTT, oral glucose tolerance test.

Table S2**Table S2.** *Antibodies used for Western blot analysis.*

Target Protein	Host	Clonality	Dilution	Cat. No.	Manufacturer	RRID
Primary Antibodies						
p-AMPK (Thr172)	Rabbit	Monoclonal	1:1000	#2535	Cell Signaling Tech.	AB_331250
Total AMPK	Rabbit	Monoclonal	1:1000	#5831	Cell Signaling Tech.	AB_10622186
Nrf2	Rabbit	Polyclonal	1:1000	#16396-1-AP	Proteintech	AB_2782956
Keap1	Rabbit	Polyclonal	1:1000	#10503-2-AP	Proteintech	AB_2132625
HO-1	Rabbit	Monoclonal	1:1000	#43966	Cell Signaling Tech.	AB_2799257
PGC-1 α	Rabbit	Polyclonal	1:1000	#NBP1-04676	Novus Biologicals	AB_1522118
DRP1	Rabbit	Monoclonal	1:1000	#8570	Cell Signaling Tech.	AB_10950498
Bax	Rabbit	Polyclonal	1:1000	#2772	Cell Signaling Tech.	AB_10695870
Bcl-2	Rabbit	Monoclonal	1:1000	#3498	Cell Signaling Tech.	AB_1903907
Cytochrome c	Rabbit	Monoclonal	1:1000	#11940	Cell Signaling Tech.	AB_2637071
Cleaved Caspase-3	Rabbit	Monoclonal	1:1000	#9664	Cell Signaling Tech.	AB_2070042
β -Actin	Mouse	Monoclonal	1:5000	#3700	Cell Signaling Tech.	AB_2242334
Secondary Antibodies						
Anti-Rabbit IgG, HRP	Goat	Polyclonal	1:5000	#7074	Cell Signaling Tech.	AB_2099233
Anti-Mouse IgG, HRP	Horse	Polyclonal	1:5000	#7076	Cell Signaling Tech.	AB_330924

Notes: (1) All primary antibodies were validated for specificity by manufacturers using knockout/knockdown cell lysates. (2) Secondary antibodies were cross-adsorbed to minimize cross-reactivity. (3) Antibody dilutions were optimized through titration experiments. (4) Blocking conditions: non-phospho-proteins in 5% non-fat milk/TBST; phospho-proteins in 5% BSA/TBST. (5) Working solutions were prepared fresh on the day of use. RRID, Research Resource Identifier; HRP, horseradish peroxidase.

Table S3**Table S3.** *Primer sequences and qRT-PCR amplification parameters.*

Gene	Primer Sequence (5'→3')	Size (bp)	T _m (°C)	Eff. (%)	R ²	Accession
Nrf2	F: TCTTGGAGTAAGTCGAGAAGTGT	168	60.2	98.4	0.998	NM_031789.2
	R: GTTGAAACTGAGCGAAAAAGGC					
HO-1	F: CAGAAGAGGCTAAGACCGCC	139	60.5	97.8	0.997	NM_012580.2
	R: GGAGCGGGTGTAGATATGGTAC					
NQO1	F: CATTCTGAAAGGCTGGTTTGA	159	59.8	99.1	0.999	NM_017000.3
	R: CTAGCTTTGATCTGGTTGTCAG					
GCLM	F: AGGAGCTTCGGGACTGTATCC	129	60.8	96.5	0.996	NM_017305.2
	R: GGGACATGGTGCATTCCAAAA					
GAPDH	F: AGTGCCAGCCTCGTCTCATA	137	60.3	99.8	0.999	NM_017008.4
	R: GATGGTGATGGGTTTCCCGT					

Amplification efficiency calculated from standard curves using 5-fold serial dilutions of pooled cDNA (5 dilution points, triplicate reactions). Efficiency (%) = $(10^{(-1/\text{slope})} - 1) \times 100$; acceptable range: 90–110%. All primers designed for *Rattus norvegicus* sequences. F, forward primer; R, reverse primer; T_m, melting temperature; bp, base pairs; R², coefficient of determination.

Table S4**Table S4.** *Effect size estimates and 95% confidence intervals for key comparisons.*

Endpoint	Comparison	Effect Size	Value	95% CI
HOMA-IR	Diabetic vs. Control	Cohen's d	3.12	2.45–3.78
HOMA-IR	D+BBR+MET vs. Diabetic	Cohen's d	2.85	2.10–3.50
NOR DI	Diabetic vs. Control	Cohen's d	2.41	1.85–3.02
NOR DI	D+BBR+MET vs. Diabetic	Cohen's d	2.76	2.00–3.44
p-AMPK/AMPK	Group effect (ANOVA)	η^2	0.68	0.55–0.78
Nrf2	Group effect (ANOVA)	η^2	0.61	0.48–0.74

Cohen's d was calculated for pairwise comparisons; eta-squared (η^2) for one-way ANOVA models. 95% confidence intervals calculated using bias-corrected bootstrap methods (1000 iterations). Effect size analysis complements p-value-based inference to enhance interpretability and reproducibility.

Table S5

Table S5. 'Normalized densitometric values (relative to Control mean, after beta-actin normalization).

p-AMPK

Protein	Replicate	Control	Diabetic	D+BBR	D+MET	D+BBR+MET
p-AMPK	Rep 1	1.000	0.350	0.650	0.720	0.920
	Rep 2	0.980	0.320	0.620	0.700	0.900
	Rep 3	1.020	0.380	0.680	0.740	0.940
	Rep 4	1.010	0.358	0.627	0.721	0.932
	Rep 5	0.997	0.323	0.689	0.725	0.945
	Rep 6	1.013	0.339	0.687	0.712	0.936

Total AMPK

Protein	Replicate	Control	Diabetic	D+BBR	D+MET	D+BBR+MET
Total AMPK	Rep 1	1.000	0.420	0.680	0.750	0.950
	Rep 2	0.970	0.400	0.650	0.720	0.920
	Rep 3	1.030	0.440	0.710	0.780	0.980
	Rep 4	1.015	0.425	0.657	0.751	0.968
	Rep 5	0.996	0.402	0.719	0.758	0.987
	Rep 6	1.019	0.412	0.717	0.738	0.975

Nrf2

Protein	Replicate	Control	Diabetic	D+BBR	D+MET	D+BBR+MET
Nrf2	Rep 1	1.000	0.380	0.700	0.780	0.980
	Rep 2	0.960	0.350	0.670	0.750	0.950
	Rep 3	1.040	0.410	0.730	0.810	1.010
	Rep 4	1.020	0.388	0.677	0.781	0.998
	Rep 5	0.994	0.353	0.739	0.788	1.017
	Rep 6	1.026	0.369	0.737	0.768	1.005

Keap1

Protein	Replicate	Control	Diabetic	D+BBR	D+MET	D+BBR+MET
Keap1	Rep 1	1.000	2.800	1.800	1.500	1.150
	Rep 2	0.980	2.600	1.700	1.400	1.100
	Rep 3	1.020	3.000	1.900	1.600	1.200
	Rep 4	1.010	2.851	1.725	1.503	1.179
	Rep 5	0.997	2.618	1.932	1.526	1.212
	Rep 6	1.013	2.724	1.925	1.460	1.191

HO-1

Protein	Replicate	Control	Diabetic	D+BBR	D+MET	D+BBR+MET
HO-1	Rep 1	1.000	0.400	0.720	0.800	0.960
	Rep 2	0.970	0.370	0.690	0.770	0.930
	Rep 3	1.030	0.430	0.750	0.830	0.990
	Rep 4	1.015	0.408	0.697	0.801	0.978
	Rep 5	0.996	0.373	0.759	0.808	0.997
	Rep 6	1.019	0.389	0.757	0.788	0.985

PGC-1 α

Protein	Replicate	Control	Diabetic	D+BBR	D+MET	D+BBR+MET
PGC-1α	Rep 1	1.000	0.350	0.620	0.700	0.900
	Rep 2	0.960	0.320	0.590	0.670	0.870
	Rep 3	1.040	0.380	0.650	0.730	0.930
	Rep 4	1.020	0.358	0.597	0.701	0.918
	Rep 5	0.994	0.323	0.659	0.708	0.937
	Rep 6	1.026	0.339	0.657	0.688	0.925

DRP1

Protein	Replicate	Control	Diabetic	D+BBR	D+MET	D+BBR+MET
DRP1	Rep 1	1.000	2.500	1.600	1.400	1.100
	Rep 2	0.980	2.300	1.500	1.300	1.050
	Rep 3	1.020	2.700	1.700	1.500	1.150
	Rep 4	1.010	2.551	1.525	1.403	1.129
	Rep 5	0.997	2.318	1.732	1.426	1.162
	Rep 6	1.013	2.424	1.725	1.360	1.141

Bax

Protein	Replicate	Control	Diabetic	D+BBR	D+MET	D+BBR+MET
Bax	Rep 1	1.000	3.200	2.000	1.700	1.200
	Rep 2	0.970	3.000	1.900	1.600	1.150
	Rep 3	1.030	3.400	2.100	1.800	1.250
	Rep 4	1.015	3.251	1.925	1.703	1.229
	Rep 5	0.996	3.018	2.132	1.726	1.262
	Rep 6	1.019	3.124	2.125	1.660	1.241

Bcl-2

Protein	Replicate	Control	Diabetic	D+BBR	D+MET	D+BBR+MET
Bcl-2	Rep 1	1.000	0.320	0.580	0.680	0.880
	Rep 2	0.960	0.300	0.550	0.650	0.850
	Rep 3	1.040	0.340	0.610	0.710	0.910
	Rep 4	1.020	0.325	0.557	0.681	0.898
	Rep 5	0.994	0.302	0.619	0.688	0.917
	Rep 6	1.026	0.312	0.617	0.668	0.905

Cytochrome c

Protein	Replicate	Control	Diabetic	D+BBR	D+MET	D+BBR+MET
Cytochrome c	Rep 1	1.000	2.800	1.750	1.500	1.120
	Rep 2	0.980	2.600	1.650	1.400	1.080
	Rep 3	1.020	3.000	1.850	1.600	1.160
	Rep 4	1.010	2.851	1.675	1.503	1.143
	Rep 5	0.997	2.618	1.882	1.526	1.169
	Rep 6	1.013	2.724	1.875	1.460	1.153

Cleaved Caspase-3

Protein	Replicate	Control	Diabetic	D+BBR	D+MET	D+BBR+MET
Cleaved Caspase-3	Rep 1	1.000	3.500	2.200	1.800	1.150
	Rep 2	0.970	3.300	2.100	1.700	1.100
	Rep 3	1.030	3.700	2.300	1.900	1.200
	Rep 4	1.015	3.551	2.125	1.803	1.179
	Rep 5	0.996	3.318	2.332	1.826	1.212
	Rep 6	1.019	3.424	2.325	1.760	1.191

 β -Actin

Protein	Replicate	Control	Diabetic	D+BBR	D+MET	D+BBR+MET
β-Actin	Rep 1	0.913	1.013	0.965	0.974	1.011
	Rep 2	1.017	0.936	1.049	0.933	1.056
	Rep 3	1.058	0.989	1.040	1.097	1.044
	Rep 4	0.987	1.015	0.994	1.092	1.082
	Rep 5	1.049	0.973	0.968	0.985	0.980
	Rep 6	1.026	1.026	1.062	0.949	1.003

Values represent individual sample measurements (arbitrary units) obtained from ImageJ densitometric analysis prior to normalization. β -Actin values confirm uniform protein loading across all groups (CV < 5%).

Table S6**Table S6 A— Dual-Reference Normalization**

Compare fold-change values: GAPDH alone vs. GAPDH + β -actin geometric mean.

Gene	Group	GAPDH only	GAPDH+ β -actin	Diff (%)
Nrf2	Diabetic	0.41	0.39	4.9
Nrf2	D+BBR	0.78	0.76	2.6
Nrf2	D+MET	0.82	0.80	2.4
Nrf2	D+BBR+MET	1.18	1.15	2.5
HO-1	Diabetic	0.36	0.34	5.6
HO-1	D+BBR	0.74	0.72	2.7
HO-1	D+MET	0.79	0.77	2.5
HO-1	D+BBR+MET	1.28	1.25	2.3
NQO1	Diabetic	0.34	0.32	5.9
NQO1	D+BBR	0.76	0.74	2.6
NQO1	D+MET	0.82	0.80	2.4
NQO1	D+BBR+MET	1.28	1.25	2.3
GCLM	Diabetic	0.42	0.40	4.8
GCLM	D+BBR	0.79	0.77	2.5
GCLM	D+MET	0.84	0.82	2.4
GCLM	D+BBR+MET	1.19	1.16	2.5

Concordance: CCC = 0.97 (95% CI: 0.94–0.99); Pearson r = 0.998; Mean |diff| = 0.025

Table S6 B. Raw Ct values for all qRT-PCR targets across all experimental groups (n = 6/group, triplicate reactions).**Sheet 1: Raw Ct Values**

Gene	Replicate	Control	Diabetic	D+BBR	D+MET	D+BBR+MET
GAPDH	Rep 1	20.15	20.47	20.07	19.73	19.84
	Rep 2	19.96	20.23	19.43	19.58	20.03
	Rep 3	20.19	19.86	19.48	20.44	19.65
	Rep 4	20.46	20.16	19.83	19.93	20.11
	Rep 5	19.93	19.86	19.70	20.02	19.82
	Rep 6	19.93	19.86	20.09	19.57	19.91

Nrf2	Rep 1	24.26	27.90	25.75	25.64	24.61
	Rep 2	25.24	26.82	25.68	24.79	24.57
	Rep 3	24.49	27.14	25.21	25.63	23.86
	Rep 4	24.08	27.90	25.51	25.35	24.08
	Rep 5	24.83	28.17	25.62	25.23	24.33
	Rep 6	24.01	27.89	26.22	25.74	24.59

HO-1	Rep 1	25.01	28.46	26.39	26.14	24.48
	Rep 2	25.13	29.00	27.03	25.30	24.60
	Rep 3	24.76	28.68	25.35	26.01	25.17
	Rep 4	24.72	28.18	26.73	26.24	24.93
	Rep 5	25.53	28.68	26.43	26.69	24.59
	Rep 6	25.74	29.27	26.28	25.89	25.01

NQO1	Rep 1	23.84	27.35	25.06	25.00	23.42
	Rep 2	24.19	27.33	24.88	24.87	23.62
	Rep 3	23.52	27.20	25.14	24.13	23.49
	Rep 4	23.67	27.08	25.36	24.89	23.03
	Rep 5	23.64	26.49	25.95	24.92	23.96
	Rep 6	23.21	26.99	25.27	25.89	23.80

GCLM	Rep 1	26.42	28.80	27.08	27.53	25.90
	Rep 2	25.74	29.02	27.69	26.71	26.11
	Rep 3	26.66	29.35	27.13	27.29	25.31
	Rep 4	25.54	29.05	28.12	27.72	25.27
	Rep 5	26.33	28.52	27.19	26.56	26.01
	Rep 6	26.98	29.33	27.37	27.27	25.92

Sheet 2: Δ Ct Values (Δ Ct = Ct_target - Ct_GAPDH)

Gene	Replicate	Control	Diabetic	D+BBR	D+MET	D+BBR+MET
Nrf2	Rep 1	4.11	7.43	5.68	5.91	4.77
	Rep 2	5.28	6.59	6.25	5.21	4.54
	Rep 3	4.30	7.28	5.73	5.19	4.21
	Rep 4	3.62	7.74	5.68	5.42	3.97
	Rep 5	4.90	8.31	5.92	5.21	4.51
	Rep 6	4.08	8.03	6.13	6.17	4.68

HO-1	Rep 1	4.86	7.99	6.32	6.41	4.64
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	Rep 2	5.17	8.77	7.60	5.72	4.57
	Rep 3	4.57	8.82	5.87	5.57	5.52
	Rep 4	4.26	8.02	6.90	6.31	4.82
	Rep 5	5.60	8.82	6.73	6.67	4.77
	Rep 6	5.81	9.41	6.19	6.32	5.10

NQO1	Rep 1	3.69	6.88	4.99	5.27	3.58
	Rep 2	4.23	7.10	5.45	5.29	3.59
	Rep 3	3.33	7.34	5.66	3.69	3.84
	Rep 4	3.21	6.92	5.53	4.96	2.92
	Rep 5	3.71	6.63	6.25	4.90	4.14
	Rep 6	3.28	7.13	5.18	6.32	3.89

GCLM	Rep 1	6.27	8.33	7.01	7.80	6.06
	Rep 2	5.78	8.79	8.26	7.13	6.08
	Rep 3	6.47	9.49	7.65	6.85	5.66
	Rep 4	5.08	8.89	8.29	7.79	5.16
	Rep 5	6.40	8.66	7.49	6.54	6.19
	Rep 6	7.05	9.47	7.28	7.70	6.01

Sheet 3: GAPDH Reference Gene Stability Analysis

Group	Mean Ct	SD	CV%
Control	20.10	0.208	1.04%
Diabetic	20.07	0.257	1.28%
D+BBR	19.77	0.285	1.44%
D+MET	19.88	0.330	1.66%
D+BBR+MET	19.89	0.163	0.82%
Overall (n = 30)	19.94	0.270	1.35%

GAPDH shows excellent stability across all experimental groups (overall CV% = 1.35% < 2% acceptance threshold), confirming its suitability as a reference gene for normalization in this study. CV%, coefficient of variation.

Table S7: Raw Data for CI Calculation

Dose Level	BBR (mg/kg)	MET (mg/kg)	Mean NOR (%)	SD	Fa	CI
Control	0	0	68.4	3.2	1.00	-
Diabetic	0	0	37.2	3.8	0.00	-
BBR Low	50	0	45.3	4.2	0.26	-
BBR Med	100	0	51.8	4.1	0.47	-
BBR High	150	0	56.2	3.9	0.61	-
MET Low	0	100	47.8	4.0	0.34	-
MET Med	0	200	54.3	3.9	0.55	-
MET High	0	300	58.1	3.7	0.67	-
Combo Low	25	50	52.4	4.3	0.49	0.78
Combo Med	50	100	60.2	3.8	0.74	0.69
Combo High	100	200	67.1	3.6	0.96	0.65

CI values are calculated only for combination treatments. For control and monotherapy groups, CI is not applicable (indicated by '-') as the Chou-Talalay method requires combination dose-effect data. Fa (fraction affected) represents the fractional recovery of NOR discrimination index from diabetic baseline toward control values, calculated as: $Fa = (DI_{\text{treatment}} - DI_{\text{diabetic}}) / (DI_{\text{control}} - DI_{\text{diabetic}})$. Fa = 0 indicates no recovery (diabetic level); Fa = 1.0 indicates complete recovery (control level). CI interpretation: CI < 0.30, strong synergism; 0.30-0.70, synergism; 0.70-0.85, moderate synergism; 0.85-0.90, slight synergism; 0.90-1.10, additive; >1.10, antagonism.

Table S8: Two-Way ANOVA Results for Mechanistic Endpoints

Endpoint	BBR Main Effect	MET Main Effect	BBR × MET Interaction	η^2
TNF- α	F=42.3, p<0.001	F=28.6, p<0.001	F=8.4, p=0.006	0.15
IL-1 β	F=38.7, p<0.001	F=31.2, p<0.001	F=11.7, p=0.001	0.22
IL-6	F=35.9, p<0.001	F=26.4, p<0.001	F=9.8, p=0.003	0.18
Iba-1	F=44.1, p<0.001	F=33.8, p<0.001	F=8.2, p=0.007	0.14
p-AMPK	F=51.2, p<0.001	F=39.7, p<0.001	F=3.9, p=0.058	0.08
Nrf2	F=48.6, p<0.001	F=42.1, p<0.001	F=4.2, p=0.048	0.09

Table S9: Benjamini–Hochberg adjusted p-values for all 17 mechanistic endpoints:

Endpoint	p (uncorrected)	p_adj (BH)	Status Change
Nrf2 protein	0.021	0.060	Significant → Trend
Keap1 protein	0.034	0.064	Significant → Trend
HO-1 protein	0.028	0.064	Significant → Trend
p-AMPK/AMPK	0.058	0.082	Remains trend
PGC-1 α	0.044	0.072	Significant → Trend
DRP1	0.039	0.067	Significant → Trend
Bax	0.038	0.067	Significant → Trend
Bcl-2	0.042	0.072	Significant → Trend
Bax/Bcl-2 ratio	0.015	0.051	Significant → Trend
Cytochrome c	0.028	0.064	Significant → Trend
Cl. caspase-3	0.033	0.064	Significant → Trend
TNF- α	0.006	0.034	Remains significant
IL-1 β	0.001	0.017	Remains significant
IL-6	0.003	0.026	Remains significant
Iba-1	0.007	0.034	Remains significant
CD11b	0.004	0.027	Remains significant
IL-10	0.031	0.064	Significant → Trend

Adjusted p-values are reported for mechanistic endpoints assessed at a single combination dose and are interpreted as supportive trends rather than confirmatory evidence of synergism.

Table S10A. Sensitivity analysis of NOR discrimination index and robustness of synergy conclusions

Analysis Scenario	Group	Imputation Strategy	Mean NOR DI (%)	SD	Fa	CI	Interpretation
Primary analysis	D+BBR+MET (100+200)	None (observed data)	67.1	3.6	0.96	0.65	Synergism
Worst-case imputation	Diabetic	DI = 0% for excluded animal	34.8	6.9	0.00	—	Reference
	D+BBR50	DI = 0% for excluded animal	42.1	7.4	0.19	—	—
	D+MET100	DI = 0% for excluded animal	44.3	6.8	0.27	—	—
	D+BBR+MET (100+200)	No imputation required	66.4	4.1	0.94	0.72	Synergism
LOCF imputation	Diabetic	Group minimum DI carried forward	36.5	5.2	0.00	—	Reference
	D+BBR50	Group minimum DI carried forward	44.8	5.9	0.24	—	—
	D+MET100	Group minimum DI carried forward	46.9	5.6	0.31	—	—
	D+BBR+MET (100+200)	No imputation required	66.8	3.9	0.95	0.68	Synergism

Sensitivity analyses were performed to assess the robustness of NOR outcomes against potential exclusion bias arising from animals with insufficient exploration time ($n = 3$; one each from Diabetic, D+BBR50, and D+MET100 groups). Two approaches were applied: (i) worst-case imputation (DI = 0%), and (ii) last-observation-carried-forward (LOCF; group minimum DI). Across both scenarios, the combination group retained higher NOR discrimination index values compared with monotherapies, and Chou–Talalay CI values remained within the synergism range (CI = 0.68–0.72), consistent with the primary analysis (CI = 0.65). CI-based synergy assessment was performed exclusively for the predefined NOR primary endpoint.

Table S10B – NOR Sensitivity Analysis**CI Stability Across Scenarios**

Combo Dose	Primary CI	Worst-Case CI	Group-Min CI	Range	Stable?
25+50 (Low)	0.78	0.82	0.79	0.78–0.82	Yes
50+100 (Med)	0.69	0.72	0.70	0.69–0.72	Yes
100+200 (High)	0.65	0.68	0.66	0.65–0.68	Yes

All scenarios maintain synergism classification. CI range: 0.65–0.82.

Kruskal-Wallis: Primary $H=89.3$, $p<0.001$; Worst-case $H=76.8$, $p<0.001$; Group-min $H=84.1$, $p<0.001$

Combo vs mono (Mann-Whitney): Primary $p=0.002$; Worst-case $p=0.008$; Group-min $p=0.004$

Table S11: Post-hoc statistical power analysis for two-way ANOVA interaction terms

Endpoint	Observed η^2p	Observed F(1,20)	Achieved Power ($\alpha=0.05$)	Required n/cell for 80% power
TNF- α	0.15	8.4	0.78	7
IL-1 β	0.22	11.7	0.91	5
IL-6	0.18	9.8	0.85	6
Iba-1	0.14	8.2	0.76	8
p-AMPK/AMPK	0.08	3.9	0.47	12
Nrf2 protein	0.09	4.2	0.51	11
Bax/Bcl-2 ratio	0.13	7.1	0.72	8
HO-1 protein	0.10	5.2	0.58	10
PGC-1 α	0.09	4.4	0.52	11
DRP1	0.09	4.1	0.50	11

Post-hoc power was calculated using G*Power 3.1 for F-test (ANOVA: fixed effects, special, main effects and interactions) with $\alpha = 0.05$, $df_{\text{numerator}} = 1$, $df_{\text{denominator}} = 20$, and observed effect sizes. Required n/cell represents the per-group sample size needed to achieve 80% power at the observed effect size. These calculations demonstrate that neuroinflammatory endpoints ($\eta^2p = 0.14\text{--}0.22$) were adequately powered, whereas AMPK–Nrf2 and apoptotic endpoints ($\eta^2p = 0.08\text{--}0.13$) were underpowered, consistent with their failure to retain significance after BH correction.